

Darren Franceschini,

Born and raised in Ontario, Darren studied business administration and management at Brock University and obtained a BBA Degree. Darren also Studied computer programming, which eventually led him to get involved in the world of Cryptocurrency in 2011 where he began mining and trading. In late 2013 he created, marketed and managed his own cryptocurrency. Between 2011 and 2017 Darren has worked with over 100 Cryptocurrencies and ICO's focusing on their market strategy, branding and technical applications. Darren has consulted on many large-scale projects including major crypto exchanges, and bitcoin ATM companies facilitating their distribution and monetization model. Darren has had the amazing opportunity to travel the world and speak at some of the largest blockchain conferences, elaborating on his vast knowledge and experiences in cryptocurrency and blockchain technology. Furthermore, Darren proceeded to work in an upscale fast paced environment assuring client delight on projects and building a very reputable company known as Blockchain Technologies Consulting Corp (BTC Corp.). BTC Corp. has worked with over 20 companies in the ICO space and major enterprise clients, as well as key financial institutions on blockchain proof of concepts, implementations and business use cases. Darren has a strong social media following which has given him the opportunity to continue to be an active community member, assisting in the education of blockchain technology to the public, while making a positive impact on today's consumer.